

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING LINGUISTIC COMPETENCES IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

O.B. Kayumova

Teacher of Bukhara Innovation University

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Abstract. *This article describes the methodological aspects, necessity and practical significance of the development of linguistic competencies in future primary school teachers, as well as the work to be done in this regard and effective methods.*

Keywords: *linguistics, educational process, competence, level, native language, teacher, student, analysis, artistic practical texts, method, competence, pedagogue, literature, content, methodology, tool.*

Introduction. In today's society, where technology, information, and innovation are developing, a teacher must look different from a teacher of yesterday. In particular, these include the professional knowledge of teachers, computer literacy, the involvement of new methodologies in the educational process, and the implementation of innovations specific to the educational process. The reforms carried out by our state in recent years have restored the status and position of teachers, and at the same time, have placed on teachers the responsibility of continuously working on themselves and becoming personnel that meets world standards. The intended goal is to comprehensively develop young people, who are the creators of the future, and to develop our country in the true sense of the word. The preparation of a modern, knowledgeable, and creative teacher occupies an important place in the modern higher education system. The transition to program diversification has been implemented in the higher education system, and a multi-level system of basic and higher pedagogical education has been created. This is based on the following basic principles in the field of education:

- recognition of the priority of education;
- freedom to choose the form of education;
- non-discrimination in education;
- ensuring equal opportunities for education;
- the inculcation of national and universal values in education and upbringing;
- the humane, democratic nature of education and upbringing;
- continuity and consistency of education;
- the mandatory nature of eleven-year education and one-year preparation of children from six to seven years old for general secondary education;
- the openness of education to everyone within the framework of state educational standards and state educational requirements;
- the unity and differentiation of the approach to the choice of curricula; education throughout a person's life;
- guaranteed social protection of teachers in society;
- secular nature of the education system; encouragement of knowledge, abilities and talent;
- harmony of state and public administration in the education system;
- openness and transparency in the field of educational activities[1, 1-3].

Analysis of the literature on the topic. The concepts of “competence”, “competency” and “competency-based approach” began to be used in scientific and methodological literature, in applied pedagogical, psychological-pedagogical, socio-psychological and other research, as well as in the professional communication of scientists, teachers, researchers and specialists in the second half of the last century (1950-1990). Thus, according to A.A. Pecherkina, E.E. Simanyuk, Ye.L. Umnikova, “competence” as a concept appeared in the scientific lexicon in the 50s of the 20th century. Previously, its interpretation in Western studies embodied various meanings. Western researchers have placed the content of this concept primarily in the presence of abilities and skills necessary for the successful performance of a specific action in a specific subject area [2, 223].

L.I. Fishman notes that among the various definitions of competence, the following is usually understood: competence is a complex integrated quality of a person, which allows him to carry out certain professional activities[3, 112-121]. Here we are not talking about separate knowledge or skills, but about a feature that allows a person to carry out a holistic activity.

Professional competence is the readiness and ability of a specialist to methodically organize and independently solve tasks and problems in a goal-oriented manner, in accordance with the requirements of the work, as well as to independently evaluate the results of his activities. Competence is the ability to carry out professional activities within the framework of the acquired competencies, which are called “knowing the eye of the matter”, that is, to make responsible decisions and act in accordance with the requirements of the given situation, - puts forward the opinion the research scientist A.V. Tutolmin[4, 43].

Researcher A.M. Novikov interprets the concept of “competence” as an alternative concept to “professionalism”. Professionalism, according to the author, is related to technological training, while competence embodies a content that is higher than professionalism, consisting of competencies called “basic qualifications”[5, 3-8]. This includes the following qualities of a person: independence of actions, a creative approach to any work, a readiness to constantly update knowledge, flexibility of the mind, readiness for systematic and economic thinking, the ability to conduct dialogue, teamwork, and communication with colleagues. According to researcher R.S. Belaya, the current stage of educational development is inextricably linked with a competency-based approach and is essentially an attempt to establish a balance between theoretical knowledge in education and the real needs of professional and practical activity. The category of “competent approach” can be interpreted as follows: it is a set of general principles for defining educational goals, selecting educational content, organizing the educational process and assessing educational results[6, 166-170].

O.V. Galustyan also shares the same opinion: a competency-based approach provides for a reorientation of the educational process. In this case, knowledge, formed skills and qualifications are transferred to create conditions for acquiring a complex of competencies that develop the potential and abilities of a future specialist in relation to professional activity in the conditions of a market economy with a rich information-communication space[7, 49].

Research methodology. In her research work, researcher D. Pardayeva puts forward the advantages of a corrective approach in the development of linguistic competencies in future teachers (on the example of English language). She puts forward the following views: “Corrective technology develops the linguistic competence of future teachers, increases language potential, and helps to increase universal educational efforts” [8, 45-48].

The content of developing this competence helps students express their thoughts and opinions in their native language freely, clearly, concisely, fluently and intelligibly, communicate in their speech without grammatical, spelling and stylistic errors, adhering to the norms of the literary language. The education of students with these competencies in secondary schools is the responsibility of the subject “Mother Language”. However, to what extent do our current textbooks educate linguistically literate students?! As a result of the research of the scientist G. Yusupova entitled “Methodology of using blended learning in the formation of linguistic competencies of future teachers”, we can see that the familiarization, creative part, assessment stages of using blended learning in the formation of linguistic competencies of future teachers, as well as technologies for assessing the level of knowledge of Uzbek language based on international criteria, have been clarified [9, 38]. The achievement of the work is that in this study, the level of knowledge of Uzbek language of students in the educational process is justified by technologies for assessing the level of knowledge of Uzbek language based on international criteria.

T.P. Ogluzdina, from the analysis of the development of the meaning of the concept of linguistic competence in the modern theory of foreign language teaching, comes to the following general conclusion: the term linguistic competence means the combination of knowledge, skills, and abilities related to the language, which allows for the implementation of speech activity in various areas of activity in accordance with the norms of the language being studied, and can also be a factor in the development of students' language skills [10, 91-94].

At the same time: “Linguistic competence means mastering the language being studied at its levels: phonetics, lexis, word composition, word formation, morphology, simple and compound sentence syntax, and the basics of text style. If a student has an idea of the system of the language being studied and can use it in practice, he can be said to have linguistic competence [11, 98]”

E.M. Maslennikova expresses the following opinion about language and grammar. “Knowledge of vocabulary and grammar, knowledge of the form and structure of a text and statement” [12, 194-198]. What these definitions have in common is the aspect of linguistic competence as a description of language and knowledge of its linguistic form.

Analysis and results. Linguistic competence is the ability to correctly use words and sentences in the language being studied in accordance with the grammatical rules that regulate speech activity in practice, to distinguish between the correctness and incorrectness of the expression of thought in speech, that is, the concept of “linguistic competence” of a future teacher of Uzbek language is his ability to understand the units of Uzbek language, speech features, analyze language phenomena, combine parts into a whole, and be ready to build sentences based on examples.

D.I. Izarenkov most appropriately indicates three main components in this regard: linguistic, subject-specific and pragmatic competencies. In his opinion, linguistic competence is associated with the linguistic aspect of the organization of communicative units, it allows the speaker to build grammatically correct and meaningful sentences; Subject-specific competence is related to the content of speech, that is, it provides information about the subject that is the subject of speech; pragmatic competence reveals the communicative intentions of the interlocutor, the conditions of communication, and the speaker's ability to use language appropriately in specific speech situations [13, 56].

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, it is worth noting that the term linguistic competence was initially used in linguistics and methodology in the system of teaching foreign

languages, but during its short-term consistent development, its scope of application expanded, becoming the basis for the creation of new words. The process of in-depth teaching of the native language begins in the primary grades. Native language education for future primary school teachers helps to expand their thinking activity, expand the scope of independent thinking, express their thoughts orally and in writing, and form the skills and competencies to communicate freely with members of society. The fulfillment of these tasks largely depends on the professional knowledge and skills of the teacher. In order to form linguistic competencies in the native language in students, the teacher himself must first be knowledgeable in the subject of the native language. Therefore, future primary school teachers should thoroughly master the knowledge provided in higher education institutions.

Developing the linguistic competencies of future primary school teachers is a complex and multifaceted process. Through an integrative approach, practical training, individual approach, use of technologies and regular observation, teachers' linguistic competencies can be developed to a high level. For primary school teachers, these competencies are important in the process of educating students. The following pedagogical aspects should be taken into account in developing the linguistic competencies of future primary school teachers:

-language teaching should not be limited to studying grammar alone. An integrative approach should be used, combining all aspects of language teaching (reading, writing, speaking, listening). For example, by reading stories, students learn new words, learn to use them grammatically correctly, and get used to expressing their thoughts in writing.

-it is important to involve students in various speech activities, through which they can develop their linguistic competencies in practice. Through role-playing games, discussions, and team projects, students can test and consolidate their knowledge in practice.

-since the language learning abilities and needs of each student are different, an individual approach should be used. This helps students develop in accordance with their abilities and increases the effectiveness of teaching.

-it is possible to develop students' linguistic competencies by incorporating modern technologies into the teaching process. With the help of online resources, interactive programs, and mobile applications, students can consolidate their knowledge and make language learning more interesting.

-it is the teacher's task to regularly monitor and analyze the development of students, and provide individual assistance if necessary. This process allows for an accurate assessment of students' linguistic abilities and their direction for further development.

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